

THE MUKIMI STUDIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In the article the Mukimi studies in the past years and the results of scholarly researches on it have been analyzed. The contribution of Uzbek literary scholars as Hamil Yakubov, Abdulla Olimjonov, Hodi Zaripov, Hashimjon Razzokov, Ghulam Karimov, Abdurashid Abdugafurov is discussed.

Key words: Mukimi, Uzbek literature, researcher, poet, poem, to compile, to publish.

Mukimi is one of the most famous representatives of Uzbek literature of the 19th century. With his works, he continued the best traditions of Eastern literature, which is known as “Devonian literature” in the world literature. At the same time, he brought the changes in social life due to the Russian occupation to literature and contributed to its renewal. During his lifetime, his poems were spread to different cities of Turkestan, poets attached praises to them, and singers sang them. Mukimi was a poet who wrote poems about the national liberation movement and created a school with his potential and status.

The study of the poet’s work began during his lifetime. Various relationships expressed in his poems, debates and articles about them are proof of this. After the poet’s death, his collection was published for the first time in 1907 by N. Ostroumov under the name “Devoni Muqimi”. It contained brief information about the poet’s biography along with his poetic works. The author of the article, N. Ostroumov, while evaluating his personality, presents the poet to the reader in the image of a dervish, and shows that his main occupation was piety and writing poetry. It is not difficult to see that under this lies an attempt to cut off the poet from the people. In 1910, the second edition of the poet’s works was made in Pordev lithography under the name “Devoni Muqimiy maa hajviyot”. In 1912, the third edition of Muqimi’s works under the above title appeared. The falsification of the poet’s works, unfortunately, continued in the next two editions, too.

The events of the period accelerated the changes of social opinion. As philosophers say, the right is getting right and the left is fading. In 1915-1916, the fanatical part of the religious people found the poets who wrote on romantic themes guilty of the violation of social morality (for example, the increase of prostitution, peddling, and extortion). In 1916, “Al-Islah” magazine opened a whole debate on this topic. On behalf of religious leaders, he went so far as to call Muqimi’s and Furqat’s poems unacceptable.

The study of the poet's work in volume and on a large scale began in the 30's of the last century. During this period, the collection, study, and publication of Mukimi's works were carried out intensively and effectively. A number of articles were published in newspapers and magazines. The prominent poet Gafur Ghulam was at the head of this good work. On his initiative, in 1938 "Mukimiy Collection" was compiled and published. In 1950, the poet's works were published in Russian in Moscow under the name "Lyrics and Satire".

In 1953, on the occasion of the 50th anniversary of Mukimi's death, a number of studies were made about him and the foundation of Mukimi studies was laid. Scientists such as Hamil Yakubov, Abdulla Olimjonov, Hodi Zaripov, Hashimjon Razzokov, Ghulam Karimov, Abdurashid Abdugafurov created important works.

Mukimi studies mainly went in two directions: a) direct study of Mukimi's work; b) to study the poet's work in a socio-historical aspect, in comparison with the legacy of his contemporaries and predecessors and successors.

Professor Ghulam Karimov (1909-1991) made a great contribution to the study of Mukimi's work. G. Karimov is a scientist who founded the school of local studies. His first article in this regard is from "History of studying the life and work of Mukimiy" (1957) in "History of Uzbek literature" (Book 3) (1966, 1975, 1987) written for students of higher educational institutions. His researches, in particular, the doctoral dissertation "Uzbek democratic poet Mukimi and the literature of his time" which he defended in 1962, is of great value. The monograph "Life and work" is a fine example of the science of urban studies. Finally, most of the publications of Mukimi's works in Uzbek, Russian and other languages are associated with the name of Professor G. Karimov.

On the occasion of independence, regional studies reached a new level. There is a need to review and draw conclusions about the poet's complex creative path and his rich literary heritage from the point of view of independence, the interests of the Nation and the Motherland. In this regard, the followers of Professor G. Karimov are working effectively.

To conclude, it should be reiterated that the Mukimi studies have been developed so far and is in the process of continuation as well. The value of the poet's works is still attracting the researchers.

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